

Hemisection as a Conservative Approach for Management of Multirooted Teeth: A Case Series of Diverse Etiologies

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Abstract

Hemisection is a conservative treatment approach for preserving multirooted teeth with localized pathology affecting a single root. This case series presents the successful management of mandibular molars with different etiologies, including internal root resorption, root caries with furcation involvement, and instrument separation. In all cases, the compromised root was removed while the healthy root was retained and rehabilitated prosthetically. Favorable clinical and radiographic outcomes were observed during follow-up, highlighting the importance of proper case selection and multidisciplinary management. Hemisection can serve as a predictable and cost-effective alternative to extraction and implant therapy for preservation of natural dentition.

Keywords: Hemisection, Furcation involvement, Internal root resorption, Instrument separation.

Introduction

Preservation of natural dentition remains a primary objective in modern dentistry, as tooth loss can adversely affect function and overall well-being.¹ Advances in endodontic, periodontal, and restorative disciplines now allow retention of teeth previously considered non-restorable through a multidisciplinary approach.²

Multirooted teeth, particularly mandibular molars, often present with localized pathology affecting a single root due to caries, periodontal disease, internal resorption, or iatrogenic complications such as instrument separation.³ In such cases, complete extraction may be unnecessarily aggressive when the remaining root has adequate periodontal support.

Hemisection is a conservative procedure involving removal of the diseased root along with its coronal portion while preserving the healthy segment. It helps maintain alveolar bone, proprioception, and function, making it a cost-effective alternative to extraction and implants.

Indications include localized bone loss, furcation involvement, root caries, resorption, fractures, and irretrievable instruments, whereas inadequate bone support,

unfavorable root anatomy, and poor compliance are contraindications.⁶ Successful outcomes depend on proper case selection and multidisciplinary management, with studies reporting favorable long-term prognosis.

This case series highlights the role of hemisection as a conservative treatment modality in mandibular molars with different etiologies, emphasizing its clinical relevance in preserving natural dentition.

Case Presentation

Case 1

A 62-year-old male patient reported to the Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics, with the chief complaint of pain in the lower left back tooth region for one month. The pain was dull in nature and aggravated on mastication.

The patient's medical and dental histories were non-contributory. Clinical examination revealed mesioproximal caries in relation to tooth 36, which was tender on percussion. Electric pulp testing showed no response in tooth 36, while the contralateral

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tooth ⁽⁴⁶⁾ responded normally. Radiographic examination revealed a gross carious lesion with an oval-shaped radiolucency in the mesial root suggestive of internal root resorption, along with widening of the periodontal ligament space indicative of apical periodontitis.

Figure 1 (a): Preoperative radiograph w.r.t. 36

The final diagnosis was: Pulp necrosis with symptomatic apical periodontitis associated with internal root resorption in the mesial root and mesioproximal caries in relation to 36. Considering the structural compromise of the mesial root and adequate periodontal support of the distal root, hemisection was planned after obtaining written informed consent.

Written informed consent was obtained. Prior to initiating treatment, oral prophylaxis was performed. Tooth 36 was isolated using a rubber dam. Access cavity preparation was carried out using a round bur and Endo access bur. A single canal was located in the distal root (D), and working length was determined radiographically. Irrigation was performed using 5.25% sodium hypochlorite, followed by 0.9% normal saline.

Figure 1 (b): Working length determination w.r.t. 36

Biomechanical preparation of the distal canal was completed up to F1 ProTaper hand file (Dentsply Maillefer,

Switzerland). The canal was irrigated with 2% chlorhexidine, and calcium hydroxide (Prime RC Cal, India) was placed as an intracanal medicament. The access cavity was temporarily sealed, and the patient was recalled after seven days.

At the subsequent visit, the canal was irrigated with saline followed by liquid EDTA. The distal canal was obturated using gutta-percha and a resin-based sealer after radiographic verification of master cone fit. The mesial canals were not treated as the mesial root was planned for resection, and the access cavity was temporarily restored.

Figure 1 (c): (i) Master cone fit in the distal canal w.r.t. 36 (ii) Obturated distal root sealed with temporary restorative material w.r.t. 36

During the third visit, under local anesthesia, a mucoperiosteal flap was reflected using a periosteal elevator. A vertical cut was made through the crown in the direction of the furcation using a tapered carbide bur to separate the mesial and distal roots. The mesial hemisected portion of tooth 36 was removed using mandibular molar forceps. Complete separation and removal were confirmed clinically and radiographically.

The extraction socket was thoroughly debrided and irrigated with sterile saline. As adequate hemostasis was achieved and soft tissue approximation was satisfactory, suturing was not performed. A sterile pressure pack was placed, and postoperative instructions were given.

Figure 1 (d) : (i) Resection of mesial root w.r.t. 36 using the vertical cut technique (ii) Immediate postoperative radiograph showing extraction socket after mesial root removal w.r.t. 36

The patient was recalled after one week for follow-up. To allow complete healing and resolution of inflammation, restorative procedures were deferred for an additional week. Core build-up of the retained distal segment was performed using glass ionomer cement. The patient was subsequently advised for full-coverage crown prosthesis.

Figure 1 (e): (i) Radiographic follow-up at three months showing the healed extraction socket of the mesial root w.r.t.36 (ii) Radiograph showing follow-up at six months w.r.t. 36.

At the 6-month follow-up, clinical evaluation revealed absence of pain and mobility. Radiographic examination demonstrated satisfactory healing of the extraction socket associated with the mesial root and adequate periodontal support around the retained distal root.

Case 2

A 37-year-old female patient reported to the Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics, with the chief complaint of pain in the lower right back tooth region for 15 days. The pain was dull, intermittent in nature, and aggravated on mastication. The patient’s medical and dental histories were non-contributory. Clinical examination revealed distoproximal caries in relation to tooth 46, which was tender on percussion. Electric pulp testing showed no response in tooth 46, while the contralateral tooth (36) responded normally.

Radiographic examination revealed a gross carious lesion involving enamel, dentin, and pulp, extending into the distal root with associated furcation involvement. Widening of the periodontal ligament space was observed in the apical region, suggestive of apical periodontitis.

Figure 2 (a): Preoperative radiograph w.r.t.46

The final diagnosis was: Pulp necrosis with symptomatic apical periodontitis associated with root caries and furcation involvement in relation to 46.

Considering the extensive furcation involvement and structural compromise of the distal root, along with adequate periodontal support of the mesial root, hemisection was planned after obtaining written informed consent.

Following oral prophylaxis and rubber dam isolation, access cavity preparation was performed using a round bur and Endo access bur. Three canals mesiobuccal (MB), mesiol-lingual (ML), and distal (D) were located, and working length was determined radiographically. Irrigation was carried out using 5.25% sodium hypochlorite followed by 0.9% normal saline.

Figure 2 (b): Working length determination w.r.t. 46

Biomechanical preparation was carried out up to F1 Pro-Taper rotary file (Dentsply Maillefer, Switzerland), followed by irrigation with 2% chlorhexidine. Calcium hydroxide was placed as an intracanal medicament, and the access cavity was temporarily sealed. The patient was recalled after seven days.

At the subsequent visit, irrigation was performed using saline followed by liquid EDTA. The mesial canals (MB and ML) were obturated using gutta-percha and a resin-based sealer, while the distal canal was left unobturated as the distal root was planned for resection. The access cavity was restored with glass ionomer cement.

Figure 2 (c): (i) Master cone fit in the mesial canal w.r.t. 46 (ii) Obturated mesial root sealed with temporary restorative material w.r.t. 46

During the third visit, under local anesthesia, a mucoperiosteal flap was reflected using a periosteal elevator. A vertical cut was made through the crown in the direction of the furcation using a tapered carbide bur to separate the mesial and distal roots. The distal hemisected portion of tooth 46 was removed using mandibular molar forceps. Complete separation and removal were confirmed clinically and radiographically. The extraction socket was thoroughly debrided and irrigated with sterile saline. As adequate hemostasis was achieved and soft tissue approximation was satisfactory, suturing was not performed. A sterile pressure pack was placed, and postoperative instructions were given.

Figure 2 (d): (i) Resection of distal root w.r.t. 46 using the vertical cut technique (ii) Immediate postoperative radiograph showing extraction socket after distal root removal w.r.t. 46

The patient was recalled after one week for follow-up. To allow complete healing and resolution of inflammation, restorative procedures were deferred for an additional week. The retained mesial segment was restored using resin composite as a post-endodontic core build-up. The patient was subsequently advised for full-coverage crown prosthesis.

Figure 2 (e): (i) Radiographic follow-up at three months showing the healed extraction socket of the distal root w.r.t.46 (ii) Radiograph showing follow-up at six months w.r.t. 46.

At the 6-month follow-up, clinical evaluation revealed absence of pain and mobility. Radiographic examination

demonstrated satisfactory healing of the extraction socket associated with the removed distal root and adequate periodontal support around the retained mesial root.

Case 3

A 56-year-old female patient reported to the Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics with the chief complaint of pain in the lower right back tooth region for two months. The pain was mild, intermittent, and aggravated on mastication. The patient had a history of incomplete root canal treatment in relation to tooth 47. Clinical examination revealed a temporary restoration with tenderness on percussion. Electric pulp testing showed no response in tooth 47, while the contralateral tooth (37) responded normally. Mesioproximal caries was also observed in relation to tooth 48, for which root canal treatment was planned.

Radiographic examination revealed a separated instrument in the distal canal extending beyond the apex.

Figure 3 (a): Preoperative radiograph w.r.t. 47

Based on clinical and radiographic findings, the diagnosis was: Previously initiated therapy with symptomatic apical periodontitis associated with a separated instrument in the distal root in relation to 47.

Considering the presence of an irretrievable instrument fragment in the apical third of the distal root and better periodontal support of the mesial root, hemisection was planned.

Tooth 47 was isolated under rubber dam, and the access cavity was refined. Working length determination for the mesial canals was performed radiographically. Biomechanical preparation was completed up to F1 using rotary files (Dentsply Maillefer, Switzerland). Irrigation was carried out using 5.25% sodium hypochlorite followed by saline, and calcium hydroxide intracanal medicament was placed for 7 days.

Figure 3 (b): Working length determination w.r.t. 47

At the subsequent visit, the temporary restoration was removed, and irrigation was performed using saline followed by liquid EDTA. Master cone selection was done using gutta-percha, and a radiograph was taken to verify the fit. The mesial canals (MB and ML) were obturated using the corresponding master cones and a resin-based sealer. The distal canal was not obturated as the distal root was planned for resection. The access cavity was restored with glass ionomer cement.

Figure 3 (c): (i) Master cone fit in the mesial canal w.r.t. 47 (ii) Obturated mesial root sealed with temporary restorative material w.r.t. 47

During the third visit, under local anesthesia, a mucoperiosteal flap was reflected using a periosteal elevator. A vertical cut was made through the crown in the direction of the furcation using a tapered carbide bur to separate the mesial and distal roots. The distal hemisected portion of tooth 47 was removed using mandibular molar forceps. Complete separation and removal were confirmed clinically and radiographically. The extraction socket was thoroughly debrided and irrigated with sterile saline. As adequate hemostasis was achieved and soft tissue approximation was satisfactory, suturing was not performed. A sterile pressure

pack was placed, and postoperative instructions were given.

Figure 3 (d): (i) Resection of distal root w.r.t. 47 using the vertical cut technique (ii) Immediate postoperative radiograph showing extraction socket after distal root removal w.r.t. 47

The patient was recalled after one week for follow-up. To allow complete healing and resolution of inflammation, restorative procedures were deferred for an additional week. Simultaneously, root canal treatment was performed in relation to tooth 48. The patient was subsequently advised for full-coverage fixed prosthetic rehabilitation involving teeth 47 and 48.

Figure 3 (e): (i) Radiographic follow-up at three months showing the healed extraction socket of the distal root w.r.t. 47 (ii) Radiograph showing follow-up at six months w.r.t. 47

At the 6-month follow-up, clinical evaluation revealed absence of pain and mobility. Radiographic examination demonstrated satisfactory healing of the extraction socket associated with the removed distal root and adequate periodontal support around the retained mesial root.

Discussion

Hemisection is a conservative treatment approach that involves removal of the diseased root while preserving the healthy portion of a multirooted tooth, thereby maintaining function, alveolar bone, and proprioception.¹ Its success depends on proper case selection, periodontal support, root morphology, and adequate endodontic and prosthetic

management.²

The present case series demonstrates the application of hemisection in three different clinical scenarios internal root resorption, root caries with furcation involvement, and instrument separation. In all cases, the decision was based on differential prognosis between roots, where the compromised root was removed and the healthy root was retained for functional rehabilitation.

In cases of internal resorption, extensive structural loss renders the affected root non-restorable, making hemisection a predictable alternative to extraction. Similarly, in teeth with localized periodontal destruction and furcation involvement, removal of the affected root improves periodontal health and facilitates maintenance.³ In cases of instrument separation, especially in the apical third, retrieval may be difficult or risky; hemisection offers a practical solution when the fragment is irretrievable and the remaining root is sound.

Studies have reported high survival rates of hemisected molars, ranging from approximately 90% to 93% with long-term follow-up. However, failures are usually associated with poor case selection, inadequate restoration, or occlusal overload.

In the present cases, favorable clinical and radiographic outcomes were observed at follow-up, highlighting that hemisection is a reliable and cost-effective alternative to extraction when performed with careful planning and multidisciplinary management.

Conclusion

Hemisection is a conservative and effective treatment modality for preserving multirooted teeth with localized pathology. When performed with careful case selection and a multidisciplinary approach involving endodontic, periodontal, and prosthetic management, it can provide predictable long-term outcomes. The present case series demonstrates that hemisection can be successfully applied across different etiologies including internal root resorption, furcation involvement due to root caries, and instrument separation by selectively removing the compromised root while retaining the functional portion of the tooth.

Thus, hemisection should be considered a viable and cost-effective alternative to extraction and implant therapy, enabling preservation of natural dentition and maintenance of oral function.

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